

Effect of Milling on the Damping Behavior of Nano-Structured Copper

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Abstract

In the present study, elemental Cu powder was mechanically milled (MMed) for 10 hours to reduce the grain (crystalline) size in the nano-range (<100-nm). The mechanically milled powder (10h-MMed) and elemental powder without mechanical milling (0h-MMed) was consolidated by die-cold compaction and were further hot extruded at different temperatures to maintain a crystallite size within the nano range. Further, the specimen was tested by a novel free-free type suspended beam arrangement, coupled with circle-fit approach to determine damping characteristics. The characterization results helps to understand the effect of the nano size of the grains on the overall damping capacity of the bulk samples compared to a normal microcrystalline sample. Results show that the damping capacity of the material varies with the grain size of the material, which has been rationalized by the process induced microstructural changes.

Keywords A. Nanomaterial, B. Grain boundary, C. Interface, D. Anelasticity, E. Non-destructive testing.

Introduction

The potential of nanomaterials (NMs) to exhibit unusual combination of properties has been instrumental in fuelling extensive research activities across the world. More particularly, these materials have thrilled the material community due to the unconventional behavior in terms of mechanical, physical and chemical properties compared to a coarse-grain sized counterpart viz., higher hardness, higher strength and higher diffusivity [1-3]. Research shows that normal coarse-microcrystalline material behavior is approached when the grain size exceeds 100-nm [4].

Damping property of a material reflects the ability of a material to dissipate mechanical energy. The dissipation of the mechanical energy takes place through the means of different energy transformation such as mechanical energy to caloric energy. In metallic specimens presence of crystalline defects, elastothermodynamic and magnetoelastic effects contribute to the total damping [5]. In addition to these mechanisms, in a NM, increased presence of microstructural defects, such as dislocations, grain boundaries, triple junctions, pores, etc., has been observed, compared to a micro-crystalline material (CM) [1]. Thus the damping study would help to understand the damping sources present and thereby describe the microstructure of the material indirectly.

Among different metallic materials, copper remains as one of the interesting material for the material community. The results of literature search have indicated that damping behavior of microcrystalline copper has been investigated [5] and the damping capacity depends on frequency, temperature and strain amplitude [6, 7]. No information, however, is available on the energy dissipation capability of nanocrystalline bulk copper synthesized using the technique of

mechanical milling (MM) coupled with hot extrusion. As mechanical milling remains one of the most industrially adaptable synthesis technique of high performance metallic materials, it is expected that the properties (such as stiffness and damping properties) of the NMs synthesized using mechanical milling will be of paramount importance to a design engineer especially for designing dynamic systems.

Accordingly, the variation in the microstructure of a NM type pure copper is studied in terms of damping capacity. The pure Cu based NM sample was prepared using the methodology of mechanical milling coupled with hot extrusion excluding sintering step. The room temperature damping behaviour was determined using a free-free type suspended beam technique utilizing frequency domain based circle-fit approach. The damping loss factor, η thus computed for a NM was further compared against the published results of coarse-grained copper samples.

Experimental Procedures

Materials and Processes

In the present work, Copper particles of 99 percent purity and less than 50 micron size (supplied by Goodfellow, England) and stearic acid (> 99.5% purity, supplied by Sigma-Aldrich, Switzerland) were used as the starting materials. The primary processing consisted of mechanical milling (MM) 50 grams of copper powder and 1 wt. % of stearic acid together at room temperature using a FRITSCH Pulverisette 5 planetary ball mill at 250 rpm for 10 hours (denoted as 10h-MMed samples). Next, the mechanically milled (MMed) powder was loaded into the 35mm-diameter compaction die lubricated by dry graphite lubricant and were subsequently cold-pressed uniaxially at 70 tons using a hydraulic press. The secondary processing consisted of hot extrusion of the cold-compacted sample at an extrusion ratio of 12.25:1 to form a 10mm-diameter extruded rod. Further, for comparison, samples without MM were made (denoted as 0h-MMed samples) by cold compaction of the elemental powder without performing mechanical milling. The extrusion pressures of 0h-MMed samples and 10h-MMed samples were maintained close to ~70 tons and ~80 tons, respectively. The extrusion die temperature was remained at 400°C throughout the extrusion process. The powder compact was heated at 700°C for 0h-MMed sample and 600°C for 10h-MMed sample. The different temperatures were used to maintain the average grain size in nanometer range and to avoid surface cracks.

X-ray diffraction studies and crystalline size calculation

The microstructural characterization of the elemental powder, mechanically milled powder and the extruded samples was performed using Shimadzu Lab-XRD-6000 X-ray diffractometer with Cu-K α radiation operated at 40 kV and 30mA, and at a scan speed of 2°C/min.

Density and Porosity Measurement

The densities of the extruded samples were measured by Archimedes' principle [8, 9]. The specimens were weighed in air and in distilled water using an HM-202 electronic balance to an accuracy of ± 0.0001 g.

Hardness measurement

Vickers microhardness was measured on the polished samples by Mitutoyo AVK-C2 automatic digital microhardness tester using 5Kgf indenting load and 15 seconds dwelling time in accordance with ASTM E92-82.

Coefficient of thermal expansion

The coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) of the extruded Cu samples were determined using an automated SETARAM 92-16/18 thermomechanical analyzer. Displacement of monolithic Cu samples (10-mm in diameter and thickness of 8-mm) as a function of temperature (50-600o C) was measured using an alumina probe under argon atmosphere and was subsequently used to determine CTE. The heating rate employed was 10oC min⁻¹ while argon gas flow rate was maintained at 1.2 lit/min.

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram showing experimental setup of suspended beam technique.

Suspended Beam Dynamic Testing

The impact-based “Free-Free” or “Suspended” beam method was performed based on the ASTM C1259-98 standard [10]. Description of the experimental setup, shown in Fig. 1, is described in reference 8 and 9. The receptance frequency response function (FRF) ‘ $\alpha(\omega)$ ’, which is the ratio between displacement response to the applied impact force, was plotted as a nyquist plot corresponding to the resonance condition [11]. Using least square technique a circle was fit, and based on hysterically damped vibrating system the circle diameter can be shown to be inversely dependent on the damping coefficient. Figs 2 (a) and (b) shows typical circle fit plots of the two NM samples. The exact location and determination of the natural frequency and the corresponding damping factor ‘ η_{free} ’ was calculated using frequency spacing technique [8, 9]. Fig. 3 shows the typical circle plot from which two points are selected for damping loss factor calculation, denoted as point a and b corresponding to frequencies ω_a and ω_b , respectively, which are lesser and greater than the natural frequency ω_n , respectively. Thus, the damping factor η_{free} can be expressed using the angles shown in Fig. 3, as follows [11]:

$$\eta_{free} = \frac{\omega_a^2 - \omega_b^2}{\omega_r^2} \frac{1}{\tan(\Delta\theta_a) + \tan(\Delta\theta_b)} \quad (1)$$

It may be noted that under low damping conditions such as in metallic specimens, equation (2) can be used to relate the loss factor η to the other damping measures, where, Ψ is the ratio between the energy dissipated during each loading cycle, ΔW , and the maximum energy stored during the cycle, W , ζ is the damping ratio, δ is the logarithmic decrement, ϕ is the phase angle between the applied stress and the resultant strain, Q^{-1} is the inverse quality factor, $A(t_1)$ and $A(t_2)$ are the displacements at times t_1 and t_2 , respectively, and f_r is the resonant frequency [7].

$$\psi = \frac{\Delta W}{W} = 4\pi\zeta = 2\delta = 2\pi \tan \phi = 2\pi\eta = 2\pi Q^{-1} = \frac{2 \ln\left(\frac{A(t_1)}{A(t_2)}\right)}{f_r [t_2 - t_1]} \quad (2)$$

Based on the ASTM standard C1259-98 [10], the dynamic elastic modulus is expressed as equation (3), in terms of fundamental natural frequency, in rad/sec, mass of the bar (m), in grams, and the beam dimensions, viz., diameter (d) and length (L), in mm. The error due to finite diameter of the bar and the Poisson's ratio of the material is accounted by the correction factor C. For bars with slenderness ratio ($k = L/d$) greater than 20, it is given by $(1+4.939/k^2)$.

$$E = 0.04069 \left(\frac{L^3}{d^4} \right) C (m\omega_n^2) \quad (3)$$

Fig. 2 Typical receptance frequency response function (FRF) showing: (a) Actual FRF data for 0-h MMed sample and (b) Actual FRF data for 10-h MMed sample.

Fig. 3 Typical receptance frequency response function (FRF) showing the natural frequency and two data points chosen to derive the damping factor.

Fig 4. X-ray diffraction spectra of (a) MMed pure Cu powder and (b) MMed + extruded Cu at different milling durations.

Results

Grain size estimation

Fig. 4 shows the X-ray diffraction spectra of the initial powder and final extruded rod samples. Based on these XRD data, the crystalline size of the samples were calculated using Sherrer equation [12]. The estimated results of the grain size are listed in Table 1.

Density and Porosity Measurement

The results of the experimental density values are listed in Table 1.

Hardness Testing

The results of microhardness measurements carried out on the NM samples are summarized in Table 1. It may be noted that the average values of hardness of the samples has increased by ~ 186 % with a decrease in grain size by ~ 33 %.

Coefficient of thermal expansion

The results of CTE measurements in the temperature range of 50-600°C (refer Table 1) revealed that milling does not affect the CTE of the bulk-extruded copper even when the grain size difference is about 36-nm. The results are in accordance with the grain size-CTE trend predicted by researchers elsewhere [2].

Suspended Beam Vibration Testing

Suspended beam vibration testing was used in the present study to compute the damping loss factor η_{free} and the dynamic elastic modulus E_d for samples corresponding to both 0 hr and 10 hr mechanical milling condition and are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Results of microstructural and damping studies of nano-Cu samples.

Milling duration (hr)	Density (g/cm ³)	MMed powder (nm)	Grain size after extrusion (nm)	Hardness (HV)	CTE (x10 ⁻⁶ °C ⁻¹)	Dyn. elastic modulus E_d (GPa)	Damp. loss factor η_{free}
0	8.8547	156	99	53±1	21.23±0.41	128.1	0.0020
10	8.2208	25	63	152±2	21.19±0.17	109.7	0.0052

Discussion

The impulse excitation technique performed on the suspended beam is exceptionally simple and fast and has many advantages. It was found to be highly repeatable to provide FRF data and the method is non-destructive. It uses low cost instrumentation and can accommodate a wide variety of specimen configurations and sizes. Moreover, the present experimental method was designed to minimize the support energy dissipation due to strings and the aerodynamic drag on the specimen surface. The circle-fit approach was also found to be feasible in determining the damping factor from the suspended beam's FRF data in the case of pure polycrystalline Al and Mg specimens and metal matrix composite samples [8, 9].

Table 1 lists the damping loss factor of the 0 hour and 10 hours mechanically milled samples. Comparison shows that the additional milling process results in the increase of the damping loss factor and a subsequent decrease in dynamic elastic modulus. The results can be

explained based on the presence of residual stress induced due to the milling process as shown in the forthcoming paragraphs.

In general for metallic materials, different forms of damping sources exist in parallel due to various relaxation processes, such as, point defect relaxation, dislocation motion, grain boundary sliding, inclusion-matrix friction, magnetoelastic effects, and elasto-thermodynamic effects [5-7]. In addition to these mechanisms, a nano-crystalline metallic material has an increased presence of interfacial defects such as grain boundaries, triple junctions, and elastically distorted layers, compared to the conventional coarse-crystalline material [1-3]. In a NM, dislocations are said to be present in a lesser quantity and are expected to be sessile (immovable) in configuration. This is based on the theory that the existence of image forces in finite atomic ensembles tends to pull the mobile dislocations out of the grains. But TEM based deformation studies of Youngdahl et al. [13] on nanocrystalline Cu samples with grain size ~ 100 -nm shows that the dislocation activity is quite dominant and is active up to a grain size of ~ 30 -nm. In the present study, the additional milling process provided to the 10hr-MMed sample is expected to have contributed high density of sessile dislocations in the microstructure compared to the 0hr-MMed sample. Studies of Le Brun et al. [12] show that the ball milling of Cu powders results in inhomogeneous deformation that can be observed as deformation substructures (like striations) in the grains using SEM and TEM. Thus their study showed that the mechanical milling of the powders increases the microhardness by a factor of 2.5 as a result of work hardening and due to the reduction in the grain size. Similar increase in the hardness, by a factor of ~ 3 (from 53 Hv to 152 Hv) has been observed in the present study (see Table 1) with a simultaneous reduction in grain size by a factor of one-third. The effect of grain size reduction on the hardness H_v can be deduced using the Hall-petch relationship for nanocrystalline Cu up to a grain size of 5-nm [14].

$$H_v = H_o + kd^{-0.5} \quad (4)$$

where H_o and k are the material constants and d is the grain size diameter. For nano-Cu, the Hall-petch constants are found to be viz., H_o and k are ~ 0.4 GPa and ~ 9 , respectively [15]. Hence in the present study, the grain size reduction of 99-nm to 63-nm can attribute to an increase in hardness by a factor of only ~ 18 % which does not explain the experimental results of hardness showing an increase of 186 %. This clearly shows that work hardening is prominent due to high density of micro-plastic zones in the form of sessile dislocations that has accumulated in the microstructure. High resolution electron microscopy (HREM) studies of Ganapathi and Rigney [16] on nano-Cu samples have confirmed that cells bounded by cell-walls are formed due to severe deformation under sliding condition. The cell walls are full of dislocations, which arrange themselves so as to minimize energy. Thus from the above increased hardness can be seen as increased micro-plastic volume fraction.

Studies of other researchers have clearly shown the dependencies of η on temperature, frequency and strain amplitude, which provide a large amount of important information on the mechanisms of micro-plasticity on the relaxation behavior of the metallic materials [5-7]. Mulyukov et al. [17] have shown that the severely deformed sub-micron-grained copper samples exhibit exponentially varying damping capacity with an increase in strain amplitude. Their study shows that the damping loss factor of the cold worked sample was around 0.00238. Furthermore, carrying out an annealing process above the temperature of 250 °C, on these severely deformed samples, drastically reduced the overall damping capacity by a factor of 5. This clearly shows that the accumulation of the residual stress in the form of the micro-plastic zones contributes significantly to the intrinsic damping capacity of the material.

Based on the Grant-Lücke theory the energy dissipation mechanism of the sessile dislocations can be explained due to their pinned configuration by any two obstacles such as the impurity atoms or antiparallel dislocations. Thus they behave like an elastic vibrating string in an

electron and phonon environment [18]. Under low amplitude of the applied cyclic load the string vibrates to dissipate energy. Hence we find at low strain amplitude the damping is independent of the strain amplitude and is dependent only on the frequency as follows [19]:

$$Q_f^{-1} \approx \frac{a_0 B \Lambda L^4 \omega^2}{\pi^2 C b^2} \quad (5)$$

where a_0 is a numerical factor of order 1, B is the damping constant, ω is the operating frequency, L is the effective dislocation loop length which depends on the pinning distance, C is the dislocation line tension ($\approx 0.5Gb^2$), G is the shear modulus, b is burgers vector and Λ is the total dislocation density. This shows that the damping depends on the dislocation density, frequency of cyclic stress and burgers vector b of the bulk material [18, 19].

Based on the theory of anelasticity, presence of the internal dislocations can also be inferred in the form of a decrement in the elastic modulus, which can be expressed as follows:

$$\frac{\Delta E}{E} = A \Lambda L^2 \quad (6)$$

where A is a material constant. From Table 1, a decrement of 14% between the 0h-MMed sample and 10h-MMed sample can be observed in terms of elastic modulus, which indirectly confirms the presence of high dislocation density.

In addition to the above discussions on dislocation density, grain boundaries in a metallic material are also considered as defects since they are not in a perfect crystalline condition and lack long-range periodicity found in a typical crystal [6]. Based on a spherical or a cubical grain shape assumption, the volume fraction of nanocrystalline materials associated with the boundaries ‘ V ’ can be calculated [1]:

$$V = \frac{3\lambda}{d} \quad (7)$$

where λ is the average grain boundary thickness and d is the average grain diameter. Generally in a nano-material the grain boundary thickness varies from 0.5-1 nm [4]. Hence compared to a polycrystalline sample containing 10- μ m grain size, a 60-nm nano-sample can contain as much as 5% of atoms in the grain boundary region while the polycrystalline sample is expected to contain only 0.03% of atoms. Such non-crystalline nature are synonymous to amorphous condition under definition, and are condensed phases that are not in thermodynamic equilibrium [21, 22]. These solids, behave similar to the polymeric materials that are known to exhibit viscoelastic material behaviour. Experiments have been conducted on pure amorphous metallic materials which exhibit clear glassy state, evidenced by a discontinuous change in the thermo-physical properties, such as, the shear modulus, heat capacity, coefficient of expansion thermal, etc [21, 22]. In the NM, such a frequency dependent behavior can be seen based on the mechanical spectroscopic studies of Bonneti et al.[23]. The anelasticity due to grain boundaries in metals is because of viscous nature, which transforms the mechanical energy in to caloric energy [6]. Ke’s damping study on single crystal versus polycrystalline aluminium clearly shows that increased presence of grains increases the damping tremendously at high temperature around 200-300° C [24]. In the present study, the experiments are performed at room temperature and hence the grain boundary sliding can be presumed to be insignificant based on a coarse polycrystalline material model. But according to Siegel [25], grain boundary diffusion and grain boundary sliding are enhanced in a NM and hence the validity of Ke’s studies may need to be investigated further for a nano-crystalline microstructure. Literature review shows that the damping measurement results of copper with coarse-crystalline microstructure and single-crystal microstructure are 0.0011 [26] and 0.0003 [5], respectively. In the present study, the 0h-MMed sample, which is expected to have relatively lesser residual stresses compared to 10h-MMed sample and belongs to a class of NM, exhibits a damping loss factor of 0.0020. But care should be taken to account the increased

presence of nano-pores in the grain boundaries in a NM material [1], on the damping capacity of the matrix [27]. To understand the effect of grain boundary on mechanical properties, the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) can be taken for investigation. The CTE exhibits the combined expansion behavior of the grains and the grain boundaries in a metallic material. In the present study, the thermal expansion of both 0hr and 10hr MMed samples exhibits similar CTE results of $21.2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and are higher than the CTE results of both single-crystalline Cu sample and coarse-crystalline Cu sample which are around $16 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ [28] and $17 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ [29], respectively. Thus the presence of increased volume fraction of grain boundary in the NM sample can be seen in increasing the damping loss factor and thermal expansion behavior on a relative scale.

In addition to the above damping mechanisms, extrinsic damping sources exist under a cyclic load in a metallic material. Zener's research showed that when a material is stressed in a reversible adiabatic process, thermal gradient is induced in accordance with the Thomson effect [30]. Heat conducts from the high temperature regions to the low-temperature regions. However small this temperature increase, this is viewed as a loss of energy and is known as elasto-thermodynamic damping (ETD) [30]. In the present study, using the thermo-mechanical properties of copper the magnitude of the ETD was predicted using the appropriate ETD model [31] and was found to be of the order of 10^{-5} due to the beam dimensions (which was 10mm) and the resonant frequency magnitude (which was around 700 Hz), that does not seem to be significant to explain the experimental observation.

The results of the present study, in essence, reveal that the circle-fit approach when combined with the impact-based measurement of the free-free type suspended beam is capable of measuring damping loss factor of the copper based NMs. Presently, further work is in progress on other monolithic NMs to further strengthen the viability of this approach. Furthermore, research is in-progress to understand the frequency and temperature dependency of energy dissipation in nano crystalline materials compared to coarse crystalline material samples.

Conclusions

Based on the present study, following conclusions may be drawn:

1. The free-free beam type flexural resonance method can successfully be used with circle-fit approach to measure the damping characteristics of bulk nanostructured copper samples.
2. Addition of the mechanical milling process step during the synthesis of the NM alters the microstructure and thereby increases the damping capacity and reduces the dynamic modulus of copper.
3. An increase in the overall energy dissipation in the case of 10h-MMed sample when compared to the 0h-MMed sample can primarily be attributed to the increase in the process induced micro-plastic zones.

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